

1 **Obesogenic diet in pregnancy disrupts placental iron handling and ferroptosis and stress**
2 **signalling in association with fetal growth alterations**

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26 **Acknowledgments**

27 The authors thank Line Zurkinden, Edgar Ontsouka and Michael Lüthi at the Institute of Biochemistry and Molecular
28 Medicine, University of Bern for their helpful support in conducting the RT-qPCR analyses. We are grateful to the staff in
29 the combined animal facility (University of Cambridge, UK) for their assistance in mouse husbandry. This work was
30 supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (grant no 310030_197408, CA) and via the NCCR TransCure (grant
31 no 51NF40-185544, CA). This work was funded by a Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council grant to
32 ALF and subsequent Medical Research Council grant to ANSP. JZ is currently financial supported by a SNSF
33 Postdoc.Mobility fellowship (P500PB_206896). JL-T currently holds a Sir Henry Wellcome Postdoctoral Fellowship from
34 the Wellcome Trust (220456/Z/20/Z) and previously a Newton International Fellowship from the Royal Society
35 (NF170988 / RG90199). ANSP was supported by a Royal Society Dorothy Hodgkin Research Fellowship, Academy of
36 Medical of Sciences Springboard Grant, Isaac Newton Trust Grant, Lister Institute Research Prize grant and the Medical
37 Research Council (DH130036 / RG74249, SBF002/1028 / RG88501, RG97390, RG93692 and MR/R022690/1/RG93186,
38 respectively).

39

40 A running title: **Aberrant iron homeostasis in obese mouse pregnancy**

41

42 **Keywords:** placenta, iron, metabolism, diabetes, pregnancy, obesity

43 **Abstract**

44 Obesity and gestational diabetes (GDM) impact fetal growth during pregnancy. Iron is an essential micronutrient needed
45 for energy-intensive fetoplacental development, but if mis-handled can lead to oxidative stress and ferroptosis (iron-
46 dependent cell death). In a mouse model showing maternal obesity and glucose intolerance, we investigated the association
47 of maternal-fetal iron handling and placental ferroptosis, oxidative damage and stress signalling activation with fetal growth.
48 Female mice were fed a standard chow or high fat, high sugar (HFHS) diet during pregnancy and outcomes were measured
49 at day (d)16 or d19 of pregnancy. In HFHS-fed mice, maternal hepcidin was reduced and iron status maintained (tissue
50 iron levels) at both d16 and d19. However, fetal weight, placental iron transfer capacity, iron deposition, TFR1 expression
51 and ERK2-mediated signalling were reduced and oxidative damage-related lipofuscin accumulation in the placenta was
52 increased in HFHS-fed mice. At d19, whilst TFR1 remained decreased, fetal weight was increased and placental weight,
53 iron content and iron transporter genes (*Dmt1*, *Zip14*, and *Fpn1*) were reduced in HFHS-fed mice. Furthermore, there was
54 stress kinase activation (increased phosphorylated p38MAPK, total ERK and JNK) in the placenta from HFHS-fed mice
55 at d19. In summary, a maternal HFHS diet during pregnancy impacts fetal growth trajectory in association with changes in
56 placental iron handling, ferroptosis and stress signalling. Downregulation of placental iron transporters in HFHS mice may
57 protect the fetus from excessive oxidative iron. These findings suggest a role for alterations in placental iron homeostasis
58 in determining perinatal outcomes of pregnancies associated with GDM and/or maternal obesity.

59 **Highlights**

- 60 • Maternal HFHS diet impaired placental iron deposition and transfer capacity
 61 • It reduced placental iron content and transporter gene expression
 62 • It also changed ferroptosis markers and enhanced placental stress kinase signalling
 63 • Changes were related to an altered fetal growth pattern in HFHS mice

64 **Graphical abstract**

65

66

5 × 13 cm

67 **1 Introduction**

68 Throughout the last two decades, the prevalence of gestational obesity has increased tremendously. A British National
 69 Maternity and Perinatal Audit conducted between 2015 and 2016 found that more than half of the observed pregnant
 70 women (52.7%) had a body mass index (BMI) above 25, with 21.3% registered with a BMI of 30 or more[1]. Obesity is
 71 primarily caused by increased consumption of carbohydrate- and fat-rich diets that typically contain low levels of protein
 72 and micronutrients, such as essential vitamins and iron[2]. Maternal obesity increases the risk of hyperglycaemia and
 73 glucose intolerance during pregnancy, which is defined as gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)[3–5]. Obesity and GDM
 74 also increase the risk of complications for the developing fetus and newborn, such as macrosomia, excess adiposity, preterm
 75 birth, birth injury, neonatal hypoglycaemia, and respiratory distress[6–9]. Other studies focussing on the long-term effects
 76 of obesity and GDM for the child have also found a reduction of insulin sensitivity and an increased risk to develop
 77 metabolic diseases in adulthood[10–12]. Despite this, the molecular mechanisms mediating the effect of maternal metabolic
 78 diseases, like obesity and GDM, on fetal and offspring outcomes are poorly defined[13].

79

80 A mechanism by which maternal metabolic diseases during pregnancy may impact the developing child could involve
 81 altered iron homeostasis[14]. Iron requirements progressively increase to meet the demand for erythropoiesis and iron-
 82 dependent enzymes during pregnancy. Maternal and fetal iron requirements are greatest in the third trimester due to high
 83 metabolic rate, rapid fetal brain development, as well as increased blood formation in anticipation of blood loss at birth[15–
 84 17]. Hence, pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to iron deficiency and in turn, related adverse pregnancy
 85 outcomes[18]. Previous work has suggested that increased adiposity in women affects iron metabolism, as indicated by
 86 elevated hepcidin levels and decreased absorption of dietary iron[19]. Furthermore, a longitudinal, multi-racial and
 87 prospective study found women with GDM had elevated levels of ferritin in the first trimester, and a decreased soluble
 88 transferrin receptor 1 (sTFR1):ferritin closer to the time of GDM diagnosis early in second trimester[20]. Moreover, another
 89 study found a strong positive association between elevated adiposity, GDM development and maternal circulating
 90 haemoglobin levels[21]. Finally, maternal obesity and excessive gestational weight gain are associated with compromised
 91 neonatal iron status[22,23]. However, further work is needed to understand how maternal obesity and GDM could impact
 92 iron homeostasis during pregnancy.

93

94 Pregnancy is generally considered as a state of increased oxidative stress, and excess adiposity and hyperglycaemic
95 conditions in GDM can augment the oxidative state[3,24,25]. Excess oxidative stress occurs through a disturbance in the
96 balance between the levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the availability of antioxidants, such as glutathione
97 (GSH)[26] and catalase (CAT), an enzyme responsible for the degradation of H₂O₂ to water[27]. High cellular glucose
98 levels are known to induce the over-production of superoxide by the mitochondrial electron-transport chain[28]. Moreover,
99 under conditions of glucose excess, glucose is converted to the polyalcohol sorbitol, which depletes intracellular GSH and
100 leads to increased ROS levels and lipid peroxidation[29]. Hyperglycaemia can also lead to the formation of advanced
101 glycation end products, which in turn, increase inflammation and induce cellular death and further oxidative stress[30,31].
102 Importantly, altered tissue iron handling, namely iron excess is also associated with the generation of oxidative stress and
103 oxidative damage[32–34]. Ferrous iron in the labile iron pool is highly reactive and can generate ROS by the Fenton
104 reaction that finally leads to lipid, DNA, and protein damage, as well as ferroptosis[35]. Ferroptosis is an iron-dependant
105 apoptosis-related cell death pathway characterized by the loss of lipid peroxide repair capacity by glutathione peroxidase
106 4 (GPX4) and CAT[27,35,36]. As a result, iron uptake, storage, utilisation, and efflux need to be strictly controlled to avoid
107 oxidative damage and ferroptosis activation. Several pro- and anti-ferroptosis genes regulate cellular ferroptosis levels. In
108 the case of increased ROS levels, changes to iron availability in the circulation and tissue can reduce the amount of
109 intracellular unstable iron to prevent ferroptosis[37–39].

110

111 Over the last few years, various studies have emerged suggesting there are inter-relationships between maternal metabolic
112 diseases, maternal iron status and oxidative stress that may have implications for pregnancy outcomes[14]. Both a low-iron
113 diet (35 mg/kg iron) and a chow diet including an iron chelator were able to rescue the reduced insulin sensitivity and β -
114 cell function in the *ob/ob* mouse model of type 2 diabetes[40] suggesting that the placenta has the ability to protect the
115 fetus from hepcidin-mediated iron deficiency in obese or overweight women by a compensatory upregulation of placental
116 TFR1[41]. Hepcidin (HAMP) expression is stimulated by high plasma iron and iron stores and acts by binding to and
117 inactivating the sole cellular iron exporter ferroportin (FPN1), which delivers iron from iron-acquiring cells, like
118 enterocytes to the blood circulation[42]. Small cohort studies have also found dysregulation of placental iron homeostasis
119 genes in diabetic pregnancies complicated by fetal iron deficiency, namely observed as elevated iron regulatory protein
120 (IRP1) and TFR1 expression by the placenta[43]. However, there are also reports of reduced placental expression of iron
121 transporters, ferroxidases, and iron entry regulators in GDM pregnancies[44], and hyperglycaemia has been shown to
122 decrease expression of several iron homeostasis genes and impaired iron uptake function of a placental cell line (BeWo) *in*
123 *vitro*[44]. Finally, supplementation with an anti-oxidant (selenium) was able to rescue the compromised expression of iron
124 homeostasis genes induced by hyperglycaemia in BeWo cells *in vitro*[44]. However, the impact of maternal metabolic
125 diseases, namely obesity and GDM on transplacental iron transport, its potential association with placental ferroptosis and
126 fetal development during pregnancy is scarcely investigated so far.

127

128 Here, we hypothesized that hyperglycaemia and obesity during pregnancy induce oxidative damage, ferroptotic cellular
129 stress responses and dysregulate iron homeostasis in the placenta with consequences for fetal growth. To test this
130 hypothesis, we utilized a well-established mouse model, in which mouse dams are fed a western-style high fat and sugar
131 (HFHS) diet to induce excess adiposity, compromised glucose tolerance and altered insulin sensitivity during
132 pregnancy[45,46]. Using this model, we examined maternal hepcidin levels in liver lysates, iron levels in placenta and
133 maternal liver and skeletal muscle, the expression of genes that regulate iron homeostasis and ferroptosis, and the activation
134 of pathways involved in stress signalling in the placenta. In addition, we determined levels of oxidative damage and
135 antioxidant potential in the placenta. Parameters were measured at gestational day (d) 16, when placental size and maternal
136 glucose intolerance are greatest, and at d19, when maximal growth of the fetus occurs (term is ~d20.5)[47].

137 2 Material and Methods

138 2.1 Reagents

139 All chemicals and reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich unless otherwise stated.

140

141 **2.2 The HFHS animal model**

142 All experiments were performed under the UK Home Office Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 following ethical
 143 review by the University of Cambridge Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Board. The present manuscript is based on a
 144 retrospective analysis of a previous and larger experiment, which characterised the effect of the HFHS diet on maternal
 145 adiposity, glucose, and insulin handling [48,49]. This study utilised archival samples that were available from those
 146 pregnancies and which were collected at days 16 and 19. Hence, this study represents a subset of the original larger cohort.
 147 This strategy was performed to maximize the output from each individual animal sacrificed for earlier studies and agrees
 148 with UK Home Office 3Rs directive related to experimental animal use.

149

150 In brief, male and female C57BL/6 mice were housed under a 12:12 h dark/light photocycle with free access to water and
 151 the standard chow diet [chow: fat, 11%; protein, 26%; carbohydrate, 62% (simple sugar, 7%); 15.3 MJ/kg]. At 8-12 weeks
 152 of age, 42 females were mated with males and the day a copulatory plug was found was determined as d1 (Figure 1).
 153 Pregnant females were singly housed from d1 onwards and assigned randomly to either continue feeding on the standard
 154 chow diet (n=21) or fed a diet composed of processed ingredients high in saturated fats and simple sugars [High fat high
 155 sugar (HFHS) diet: fat, 30%; protein, 17%; carbohydrate, 53% (simple sugar, 36%); 18.3 MJ/kg, n=21] (Figure 1). The
 156 details of the diets, namely nutritional composition and food intake have been reported previously[46]. According to the
 157 manufacturer, the diets contained 188mg/kg and 49mg/kg iron content, respectively. Based on the daily food intake of the
 158 dams[46], daily iron intake was ~0.827mg/day for the control chow and ~0.162mg/day for the HFHS diet-fed mice. On
 159 d16 or d19, dams were anaesthetized (intraperitoneal injection of 10ul/g fentanyl-fluanisone, midazolam [Janssen Animal
 160 Health, Belgium] in sterile water, 1:1:2), and then schedule 1 killed by cervical dislocation. Maternal organs (liver, kidneys,
 161 heart, and skeletal muscle [*biceps femoris*]) were collected, and conceptuses were dissected. All fetuses and placentas were
 162 weighed and collected. The placenta that was closest to the litter mean was bisected and both halves were fixed in 4%
 163 paraformaldehyde for histological assessment. The remaining placentas in the litter were snap frozen as a whole and stored
 164 at -80°C for further molecular and biochemical analyses. We have previously reported that HFHS feeding did not affect
 165 litter size or viability[48].

166

167 **Figure 1: Schematic of the study design.** C57Bl/6J mice at 8-12 weeks age were mated with lean stud males. The day a
 168 copulatory plug was observed was defined as gestational day 1 (d1). On d1, females were randomly assigned to carry on
 169 either chow diet or fed the high fat high sugar (HFHS) diet until tissue collection at d16 or d19. Recording of the body
 170 weight was done at d1 and blood glucose measurement and tissue collection at the day of dissection.

171

172 2.3 Iron content analysis by colorimetric ferrozine-based assay

173 Total iron content in liver and placental tissue lysates was determined using a colorimetric ferrozine-based assay[50].
174 Placental and maternal liver tissue lysates were prepared by homogenisation in RIPA lysis buffer as described
175 previously[46]. Protein concentration in the lysates was determined using the Bicinchoninic Acid protein assay (Thermo
176 Scientific, US). Then, 100 mM NaOH was added in equal volume to the samples, before iron releasing reagent (solution
177 of equal volumes of 1.4 M HCl and 4.5% weight/volume (w/v) KMnO_4 , in distilled water) was added in two-times the
178 volume of the samples. Samples were sealed with foil and incubated for 2 hours at 60°C. After cooling the samples to room
179 temperature, iron detection reagent (6.5 mM ferrozine; 6.5 mM neocuproine; 2.5 M ammonium acetate; 1 M ascorbic acid;
180 all dissolved in distilled water) was added in a 1:10 ratio (v/v). Samples were then incubated at room temperature for
181 30 min before absorbance was measured at 550 nm using a microplate reader (V_{Max} Kinetic ELISA Microplate Reader with
182 Softmax Pro Software, Molecular Devices LLC, USA). Samples were run in duplicate and iron content interpolated using
183 a FeCl_3 standard curve. Maternal skeletal muscle iron content was determined using a QuantiChrom iron assay kit according
184 to the manufacturer's instructions (DIFE-250, BioAssay Systems, Hayward, CA 94545, USA). Iron contents were
185 normalized to the protein concentration.

186

187 2.4 Hepcidin measurement in maternal liver tissue lysate using enzyme-linked immunoassay (ELISA)

188 A mouse HAMP ELISA Kit (Article number: OKEH01408, Aviva Systems Biology, San Diego, CA 92121, USA) was
189 used to quantify the levels of hepcidin in the maternal liver. Hepcidin quantification was performed according to the
190 manufacturer's recommendations and values were normalized to the protein concentration.

191

192 2.5 Histological analysis of iron deposition by Prussian blue staining

193 Placental halves fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde were processed and embedded in paraffin wax using standard histological
194 procedures[51]. Paraffin-embedded placentas were cut at 5 μm thickness, deparaffinized, rehydrated and stained with
195 Prussian blue (1% potassium hexacyanoferrate and 1% HCl) followed by counterstaining with nuclear fast red. Slides were
196 scanned using a Panoramic Midi digital slide scanner (3DHISTECH Ltd.) and analysed under 10x magnification using
197 ImageJ (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>). In brief, images of each placental cross-section were subdivided into decidua, junctional
198 zone, and labyrinth zone, which correspond to maternal, endocrine and transport compartments of the placenta,
199 respectively. Brightness of the blue regions, representing the histochemical detection of iron, was determined by
200 automatically converting pixels in the threshold-based blue area to unweighted grayscale. The Macro-language of ImageJ
201 was used to quantify the percentage of area occupied by iron in each section by applying "Colour Thresholder 1.53e" and
202 the "Analyze Particles" functions. To measure both total tissue area (nuclear fast red positive) and iron deposition area
203 (Prussian blue positive), the threshold limits were adjusted to select and quantify the blue iron-positive and the magenta
204 area of the section as background. Finally, the iron deposition area in all three placental zones was normalized to the
205 background within each section.

206

207 2.6 Histochemical lipofuscin detection by Sudan Black B staining

208 Sudan-Black-B (SBB) stains lipofuscin, which consists of oxidized and cross-linked proteins, lipids, and metal ions,
209 including iron that accumulate in the cytosolic compartment of cells[52]. After deparaffinization and rehydration, placental
210 sections were stained with freshly prepared and filtered 60% Sudan Black B solution in ethanol (0.7% in 70% ethanol
211 [w/v]) [52] before counterstaining with Nuclear Fast Red. Slides were scanned using a Hamamatsu NanoZoomer 2.0-HT
212 slide scanner and analysed under 10x magnification. Cells exhibiting dark navy-blue intracellular particles were considered
213 lipofuscin-positive, and the percentage of SBB-positive tissue areas was determined by manual selection and subsequent
214 quantification and normalization with background using the ImageJ macro (Threshold analysis).

215

216 **2.7 RNA isolation, reverse transcription, and quantitative PCR (qPCR)**

217 Placental RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Plus Mini Kit (Qiagen, Manchester, UK) and reverse transcribed using
 218 Multiscribe Reverse Transcriptase with random primers (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). The cDNA was
 219 analysed in duplicate by qPCR using specific primers (**Table 1**), SYBR Green detection chemistry (GoTaq®qPCR Master
 220 Mix, Promega) on a ViiA7 thermocycler (Applied Biosystem) using default cycling conditions for 40 cycles (95°C for
 221 10 min, 95°C for 15 sec, 60°C for 1 min). Melting curve analysis was used to verify the absence of additional PCR products
 222 and primer dimers. The expression of genes of interest were calculated using $-\Delta C_t$ by ensuring values were normalised to
 223 the mean expression of reference genes (*Ywhaz*, *Gapdh*, *Ubi*, and *Tbp*). These four genes remained stably expressed
 224 between the groups) and represented relative to the control group mean.

225 **Table 1: Primer list**

Gene name	NCBI accession	Forward primer [5'-3']	Reverse primer [5'-3']	Product [bp]
<u>Iron endocytosis gene:</u>				
<i>Trf1</i>	NM_011638.4	GGCGCTTCCTAGTACTCCCT	ACTTGCCGAGCAAGGCTAAA	119
<u>Iron transporter genes:</u>				
<i>Dmt1</i>	NM_001146161.1	CAGGAGGTTGACTGGGTCG	GAATAGGATTCGGCTCCGCC	87
<i>Zip8</i>	NM_001135150.1	GGGACTAGCTTTCGGCATTT	GCATGTCGTTTCATCTCTGGA	122
<i>Zip14</i>	NM_001135151.1	GGACCGCTATGGAAAGAATGAC	CTCACTCGCCCCGATCTG	196
<i>Fpn1</i>	NM_016917.2	TGCAGGAGTCATTGCTGCTAG	TGGAGTTCTGCACACCATTGAT	119
<u>Oxido-reductase genes:</u>				
<i>Heph</i>	NM_010417.2	GAATTTTGCAGCCGACCTT	TCATCCGCTTTCAGATACCC	111
<i>Cp</i>	NM_007752.3	TCTTGGAAATCCTAGGTCCTGTC	TGAGGAGCGACCTGGTG	160
<i>Zp</i>	NM_001164797.1	CTACGACAAGGATTCGGAAGGAG	GGGCATCAATGTGTGAGTGG	182
<u>Iron regulator genes:</u>				
<i>Hamp</i>	NM_032541.2	CAGGGCAGACATTGCGATAC	TGCAACAGATAACCACACTGGG	113
<i>Hfe</i>	NM_010424.5	CAGCTGAGGACATGAGCCTA	GTATCTTAGAGAATGTGAACGCGG	119
<u>Iron sensing, mRNA binding genes:</u>				
<i>Irp1</i>	NM_007386.2	AGCCTTTGGGAGTGAACGC	GATGACATGCTGCCTTTCCAC	98
<i>Irp2</i>	NM_022655.3	CCGGGATCGTGTGATTCTG	ACACTGTCTCAGGTTTCAGGC	122
<u>Anti-ferroptotic genes:</u>				
<i>Cat</i>	NM_009804.2	AGACAATGTCACACTCAGGTGCG	GCGTGTAGGTGTGAATTGCG	230
<i>Fsp1</i>	NM_012019.3	CGAGGAGTGATCGCCGAAAT	TGCTGGAACAAGTTGCCTGG	137
<i>Gclc</i>	NM_012815.2	AAGCCATAAACAAGCACCCC	CGGAGATGGTGTGTTCTTGTC	116
<i>Gss</i>	NM_012962.1	ATGCCGTGGTGTACTGATT	TCTTCGGCGGATTACATGGA	107
<i>Gpx4</i>	NM_008162.4	GTGCATCCCGCATGATTGGCG	GATTACTTCTGGCTCCTGCCTC	255
<i>Hif1a</i>	NM_001313919.2	TTGGCAGCGATGACACAGAA	TGCAGGATCAGCACTACTTCG	167
<i>Pla2g6</i>	NM_001199023.1	GTGACCGCATTCTTCTCCGT	CCCCCTGCTCTGGGTCA	377
<u>Pro-ferroptotic gene:</u>				
<i>Acs14</i>	NM_053623.1	CTCCTGCTTTACCTACGGCT	ACAATCACCCCTTGCTTCCCT	97
<i>Nox2</i>	NM_007807.5	GACACGCATGCCTTTGAGTG	CGCCTATTGTGGTGTAGGGT	262
<i>Xdh</i>	NM_011723.3	TCTATGCATCCAAGGCTGTGCG	CTGGGGAGCCTCCTTTTCAG	258
<u>Reference genes:</u>				
<i>Ywhaz</i>	NM_011740.3	TTGATCCCCAATGCTTCGC	CAGCAACCTCGGCCAAGTAA	88
<i>Gapdh</i>	NM_001289726.1	GAAGGGCTCATGACCACAGTC	CACGTCAGATCCACGACGG	227
<i>Ubi</i>	NM_019639.4	CCCACACAAAGCCCCTCAAT	AAGATCTGCATCGTCTCTCTCAC	70
<i>Tbp</i>	NM_013684.3	CCCTATCACTCCTGCCACAC	CTGCAGCAAATCGCTTGGG	158

226

227 2.8 Measurement of lipid peroxidation products (TBARS)

228 The level of lipid peroxidation was measured in tissue lysates using a thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS)
229 assay and expressed as concentration of lipid peroxidation equivalent product malondialdehyde (MDA) [53]. Briefly, the
230 lysates were precipitated by mixing with 15% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA, Merck, Germany) in 1:1 (v/v) ratio. The
231 precipitate was kept for protein carbonylation measurement (see below) and protein quantification (Pierce BCA Protein
232 Assay, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The supernatant of the sample was mixed with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) solution (0.67%
233 w/v TBA (VWR, Switzerland) in 2.5 M HCl) in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio, and boiled for 20 min at 95°C. After cooling the samples
234 to room temperature, 1-butanol was added with gentle mixing. Samples were then centrifuged at 1000 rcf and the butanol
235 layer (top phase) was retrieved for measurement in a black-wall 96-well plate using a Flex Station II fluorescence reader
236 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at an excitation/emission wavelength of 530/550 nm, respectively. MDA equivalents were
237 calculated by interpolation to an MDA (1,1,3,3 Tetraethoxypropane) standard curve. Concentrations of TBARS were
238 expressed as MDA equivalents and normalized to protein concentration.

239

240 2.9 Measurement of protein carbonylation

241 Protein carbonyl groups were measured by their reaction with 2,4-di-nitrophenyl-hydrazine (DNP)[54]. In brief, proteins
242 in placental lysates (preparation see 2.3) were isolated by TCA precipitation as described above for the TBARS assay.
243 Subsequently, 10 mM DNP in 2 M HCl was added and samples were allowed to stand for 1 hour at room temperature with
244 intermittent vortexing. Thereafter, 20% (w/v) TCA was added for precipitation, followed by three washing steps with
245 ethanol-ethyl-acetate (1:1) to remove free reagent. The precipitated proteins were dissolved in 600 μ L of 6 M guanidine
246 solution. The carbonyl content was spectroscopically determined and calculated from the optical density values at 405 nm
247 measured by a Vmax Kinetic ELISA Microplate Reader (VWR) using a molar absorption coefficient of 22'000 M⁻¹
248 cm⁻¹[54]. Carbonyl contents were normalized to the protein concentration (Pierce BCA Protein Assay, Thermo Fisher
249 Scientific).

250

251 2.10 Measurement of total glutathione levels

252 To estimate the antioxidant potential of placental lysates, total glutathione levels were quantified as described
253 previously[55]. GSH content was normalized to the lysate protein concentration.

254

255 2.11 Assessment of proteins involved in stress signalling and ferroptosis activation by immunoblotting

256 Tissue lysates (preparation see 2.3) were separated by SDS-PAGE and transferred onto 0.2 μ m nitrocellulose membranes
257 (Bio-Rad Laboratories, US) using a semi-dry technique (Semi-dry Blotter, Invitrogen) as described before[56]. Briefly,
258 membranes were stained with Ponceau red, and staining captured on an iBRIGHT gel/membrane imager (Thermo
259 Scientific, US). The membrane was washed with tris-buffered saline containing tween (TBST) and blocked with 5% milk
260 or fetal bovine serum (used for phosphorylated proteins) in TBST on a shaker, for 60 min at room temperature. Membranes
261 were then incubated overnight at 4°C using the following primary antibodies anti-Catalase (D5N7V) antibody (#14097,
262 Cell Signaling Technology, Danver, MA, USA), anti-TFR1/CD71 (D7G9X) XP antibody (#13113, Cell Signaling
263 Technology), anti-ERK1/2 antibody (#4695, Cell Signaling Technology), anti-phospho ERK1/2 antibody (#9911, Cell
264 Signaling Technology), anti-p38 MAPK antibody (#8690, Cell Signaling Technology), anti-phospho-p38 MAPK antibody
265 (#4511, Cell Signaling Technology), anti- JNK antibody (#9252, Cell Signaling Technology), anti-phospho-JNK antibody
266 (#4668, Cell Signaling Technology). Thereafter, membranes were washed and incubated with rabbit or mouse secondary
267 antibodies tagged to horseradish peroxidase (NA934 or NA931, Sigma Aldrich) diluted in TBST containing 2.5% milk for
268 60 min. Following membrane washing, protein bands were visualised using Scientific SuperSignal West Femto enhanced
269 chemiluminescence (ECL) substrate (Thermo Scientific, US) and captured on the iBRIGHT. The signal intensity of protein
270 bands was quantified using ImageJ software and normalized to the Ponceau red signal, which is indicative of protein
271 loading[56]. The abundance of phosphorylated proteins was calculated as a ratio to their respective total protein abundance.

272

273 2.12 Statistical analysis

274 Statistical comparisons and the plotting of results were performed using GraphPad Prism (GraphPad). Data are represented
275 as Tukey boxplots. In brief, the difference between the 25th and 75th percentiles is defined as inter-quartile range (IQR) and
276 represented as a box, the median as line (-) and the average as plus sign (+) in the IQR box. The limit of the upper whiskers
277 marks the largest value if this value is smaller than the 75th percentile plus 1.5 times IQR and the lower whiskers the
278 smallest value in the data set if bigger than the 25th percentile minus 1.5 IQR. Any values that fall beyond the whiskers of
279 a box-and-whiskers plot are recognized as extreme values and plotted as individual points. Statistical testing for normality
280 was performed for each data set by D'Agostino-Pearson and Shapiro-Wilk normality test. Whenever one of the data sets
281 did not pass the normality tests, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was used to compare the experimental chow-fed
282 and HFHS diet fed groups within each gestational age. For statistical analysis of maternal and conceptus biometric data,
283 two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test were applied. Unless otherwise stated, all other data
284 were analysed by Mann-Whitney test to compare the HFHS to the control chow fed group at the respective study age. One
285 to two fetuses per litter with their corresponding placenta were used to determine fetal and placental weights reported in
286 Table 2 and for all subsequent biochemical, histological, and molecular analyses. The ratios of placental and maternal liver
287 iron content were analysed using an unpaired t-test. Per group and diet, one to two placentas per litter were analyzed. A P
288 value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

289 3 Results**290 3.1 Maternal HFHS diet affects placental and fetal weight in pregnancy**

291 HFHS diet significantly reduced fetal weight on d16, whilst on d19 fetal weight was significantly increased (Figure 2A).
292 Placental weight was unaltered on d16, while on d19 placental weight was significantly decreased in the HFHS group
293 (Figure 2B). Despite this, there was not a significant change in placenta efficiency, defined as ratio between fetal and
294 placental weight between HFHS and control mice at either gestational age (Figure 2C). Previous work using this diet has
295 reported that the HFHS diet increased maternal adiposity and hyperglycaemia during pregnancy[46]. In the current study,
296 we found that the HFHS diet was associated with a non-significant increase in maternal circulating glucose concentrations
297 (fed conditions) and did not impact on the weight of key maternal organs, namely the liver, kidneys or heart (Table 2).
298 Thus, a maternal HFHS diet impacts fetal and placental growth in a gestational-age dependent manner without overt
299 changes in maternal biometry bedside the previously reported increased adiposity[46].

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Figure 2: The effect of a HFHS diet on fetal and placental growth on day 16 and 19 of pregnancy. Fetal weights (A; n=10-11/diet/age), placental weights (B; n=10-11/diet/age) and placental efficiency as calculated by the ratio between fetal and placental weight (C; n=10-11/diet/age) are presented. Data are from 1-2 fetuses per litter. Differences between HFHS and the control chow group were analysed for d16 and d19 separately by two-way ANOVA test with Tukey's multiple comparisons test; $\alpha = 0.05$, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. The individual points that are plotted beyond the whiskers of the box-and-whiskers plots are extreme values larger than the 75th percentile plus 1.5-times inter-quartile range or smaller than the 25th percentile minus 1.5-times inter-quartile range.

309 **Table 2: Effect of a HFHS diet maternal organ weights at day 16 and 19 of pregnancy**

	d16				d19			
	Control		HFHS		Control		HFHS	
	Mean ± SD	n						
Maternal data								
Body weight at conception [g]	18.47 ± 0.99	6	18.86 ± 1.84	7	19.04 ± 1.72	5	19.36 ± 2.25	5
Body weight at study age [g]	31.27 ± 3.78	11	29.78 ± 1.66	10	36.91 ± 5.59	10	34.35 ± 3.85	11
Body weight post hysterectomy (p.h.) [g]	23.81 ± 2.48	11	22.74 ± 1.40	10	25.11 ± 3.70	10	22.85 ± 2.04	11
Blood glucose fed state [mM]	10.88 ± 1.51	11	12.55 ± 2.38	10	8.68 ± 1.93	10	10.49 ± 1.84	11
Liver weight [g]	1.92 ± 0.21	11	1.75 ± 0.20	10	1.89 ± 0.35	10	1.64 ± 0.19	11
Liver (% body weight p.h.)	8.05 ± 0.32	11	7.71 ± 0.85	10	7.63 ± 1.50	10	7.20 ± 0.75	11
Kidneys weight [g]	0.28 ± 0.04	9	0.24 ± 0.02	8	0.29 ± 0.04	9	0.25 ± 0.05	10
Kidneys (% body weight p.h.)	1.15 ± 0.06	9	1.06 ± 0.10	6	1.16 ± 0.05	9	1.10 ± 0.11	10
Heart weight [g]	0.13 ± 0.02	11	0.12 ± 0.00	10	0.15 ± 0.03	10	0.14 ± 0.03	11
Heart (% body weight p.h.)	0.55 ± 0.05	11	0.54 ± 0.04	10	0.58 ± 0.06	10	0.60 ± 0.07	11

310 Data are represented as mean± standard deviation (SD). Differences between HFHS and the control chow group were
 311 analysed for d16 and d19 separately by two-way ANOVA test with Tukey's multiple comparisons test; $\alpha = 0.05$, no
 312 significance was detected.

313

314 **3.2 Maternal HFHS diet does not change maternal iron status, but affects placental iron distribution and** 315 **deposition in pregnancy**

316 Maternal hepcidin protein concentration was reduced by a HFHS diet at both gestational ages (Figure 3A). However,
 317 maternal liver and skeletal muscle iron concentration was not different between HFHS and control dams at either d16 or
 318 d19 (Figure 3B-C). At d16, placental iron content was also not altered, but at d19, it was reduced in HFHS dams (Figure
 319 3D). Placental capacity to take up iron from the mother, represented by the ratio of placental iron to maternal liver iron
 320 concentration, was reduced at d16, but found to be no longer affected on d19 in HFHS dams (Figure 3E). Placental capacity
 321 to transfer iron to the fetus for growth, as indicated by placental iron content relative to fetal weight, was similar between
 322 HFHS and control dams at d16, but lower in HFHS than control dams at d19 (Figure 3F). Histological analysis by Prussian
 323 blue staining revealed intense and numerous iron deposits in the placental labyrinth zone, with fewer in the junctional zone
 324 and decidua independent of the gestational diet (Figure 3G-H). However, focal iron deposition in the decidua was
 325 significantly lower in HFHS mice compared to control mice at d16, with no significant change observed at d19 (Figure
 326 3H). There were no differences in iron deposition in the junctional or labyrinth zones in response to a maternal HFHS diet,
 327 regardless of the gestational age (Figure 3H).

328
 329 **Figure 3: The effect of a HFHS diet on maternal hepatic hepcidin, maternal liver, skeletal muscle and placenta iron**
 330 **content and placental iron deposition on day 16 and 19 of pregnancy.** The master iron regulator hepcidin was quantified
 331 by ELISA in maternal liver lysates (A; n=5-6/diet/age). Tissue iron content was measured by ferrozine-based assay or
 332 QuantiChrom Iron kit in liver (B; n=5-6/diet/age), skeletal muscle (C; n=5-6/diet/age) and placenta (D; n=10-11/diet/age).

333 The ratio of placenta to maternal liver iron content (E; n=4-7/diet/age) was analysed as a parameter for placental iron uptake
334 capacity. The placental capacity to transfer iron to the fetus is represented by placental iron content normalized to fetal
335 weight (F). Tissue iron deposition was visualized by Prussian blue staining in mouse placenta cross-sections (G-H) and
336 analysed using Image J (H; d16 n=4-6 and d19 n=6/diet). Dec = decidua, Jz = junctional zone, Lz = labyrinth zone. Arrows
337 in G1-2 highlight blue-stained iron deposits in the decidua (G1) and arrow heads (►) focal iron deposits in the placental
338 labyrinth (G2) of a control chow placenta from d16. In all bar charts, controls are shown in blue, HFHS dams in orange.
339 Data are represented as Tukey box and whiskers and analysed by Mann-Whitney test, $\alpha=0.05$, * $P<0.05$ or by unpaired t
340 test (E). The individual points that are plotted beyond the whiskers of the box-and-whiskers plots are extreme values larger
341 than the 75th percentile plus 1.5-times inter-quartile range.

342

343 3.3 Maternal HFHS diet alters iron homeostasis gene expression in the placenta

344 The analysis of 12 important iron homeostasis genes by RT-qPCR revealed an opposing effect of the HFHS diet on
345 placental gene expression at d16 and d19 (Figure 4A-D). There was a significant upregulation of the ferroxidase hephaestin
346 (*Heph*), the iron-responsive regulatory protein (*Irf1*), and the iron transporter divalent metal transporter 1 (*Dmt1/Slc11a2*)
347 in the placenta of HFHS mice at d16 (Figure 4A-B). In contrast, at d19 *Heph* was no longer significantly altered, iron
348 transporters *Dmt1*, Zrt- and Irt-like protein 14 (*Zip14*) and ferroportin (*Fpn1*), as well as transferrin receptor (*Tfr1*) and
349 *Irf1*, were downregulated in the placenta of HFHS dams (Figure 4C-D). There was no effect of maternal HFHS diet on
350 placental mRNA levels of iron homeostatic regulators hepcidin (*Hamp*) and *Hfe* at either gestational age. Informed by
351 immunoblotting, protein levels of TFR1 (CD71) were reduced in the placenta at d16 and d19 in HFHS dams (Figure 4E-
352 F).

353
 354 **Figure 4: The effect of a HFHS diet on the placental expression of various iron homeostasis genes and proteins on**
 355 **day 16 and 19 of pregnancy.** The mRNA levels of selected iron homeostasis genes were evaluated by RT-qPCR in
 356 placental tissues at d16 (A-B; n=7-9/diet/age) and at d19 (C-D; n=6/diet/age). Data are represented as Tukey box and
 357 whiskers (A and C) and analysed by Mann-Whitney test, $\alpha=0.05$. Additionally, gene expression levels are shown as volcano
 358 plots (B and D). The abundance of TFR1 (CD71) was determined by immunoblotting (E-F; n=7/diet/age). In all charts,
 359 controls are shown in blue, HFHS in orange. The mean rank differences in the volcano plots were plotted on the x-axis,
 360 where negative values represent a down- and positive an up-regulation of mRNA levels in the HFHS relative to control
 361 placentas (blue dotted vertical line) and negative decade logarithm of the P-values are shown in y-axis, where the black
 362 horizontal dotted line represents $\alpha=0.05$ ($-\log_{10}\alpha=1.301$). * $P<0.05$; ** $P<0.01$. The individual points that are plotted beyond
 363 the whiskers of the box-and-whiskers plots are extreme values larger than the 75th or smaller than the 25th percentile ± 1.5 -
 364 times inter-quartile range.

365

366 3.4 Maternal HFHS diet results in dysregulation of ferroptosis and stress kinase signalling in the placenta

367 As informed by RT-qPCR analysis, pro-ferroptosis and oxidative stress related gene NADPH oxidase 2 (*Nox2*) and anti-
368 ferroptotic and antioxidant gene catalase (*Cat*), were significantly upregulated at d16 (Figure 5A). The mRNA levels of
369 the pro-ferroptosis marker xanthine dehydrogenase (*Xdh*) and hypoxia-inducible factor-1 alpha (*Hif1a*) which is a master
370 regulator of responses to low oxygen, but can also regulate the expression of genes involved in the execution of
371 ferroptosis[57] showed a non-significant tendency to be upregulated as well (Figure 5A, both $p=0.071$). These genes were
372 no longer altered in the placenta at d19 by a maternal HFHS diet (Figure 5B). Furthermore, the other pro-ferroptotic gene
373 analysed, namely long-chain-fatty-acid-CoA ligase 4 (*Acs14*), and other anti-ferroptotic genes assessed, in particular,
374 ferroptosis suppressor protein 1 (*Fsp1*), glutamate-cysteine ligase (*Gclc*), glutathione synthetase (*Gss*), and calcium-
375 independent phospholipase A2 beta (*Pla2g6*), were unaltered in the placenta at either d16 or d19 when comparing HFHS
376 fed versus control placentas (Figure 5A-B). However, ferroptosis is also mediated via changes in stress protein signalling
377 pathways, namely the extracellular signal regulated kinase (ERK), c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) and mitogen activated
378 protein (MAP) kinase p38 families[58]. Hence, their abundance and activation levels in the placenta in response to a
379 maternal HFHS diet were analysed by immunoblotting (Figure 5C-F). This analysis revealed a significant upregulation of
380 ERK2 and p38 proteins, in addition to elevated phosphorylated (activated) JNK1 and p38 in the placenta of HFHS mice at
381 d16 (Figure 5C and E) and at d19 (Figure 5D and F). The upregulation of total ERK2 and phosphorylated p38 persisted
382 until d19, while JNK1 total protein was increased in the placentas of HFHS mice at d19 only. The protein abundance of
383 CAT although not different at d16, was found to be significantly upregulated in the placenta of HFHS mice at d19.

384
 385 **Figure 5: The effect of a HFHS diet on genes and proteins involved in ferroptosis in the placenta at days 16 and 19**
 386 **of pregnancy.** The expression of ferroptosis-specific genes was determined by RT-qPCR (A-B; n=3-9/diet/age).
 387 Immunoblots with corresponding Ponceau S pictures are shown for d16 and d19 (C-D; n=7/diet/age). The respective
 388 quantification of signalling proteins is displayed relative to the control group means (E-F). Data were analysed by Mann-
 389 Whitney test, with $\alpha=0.05$ and are represented as Tukey box and whiskers and normalized to the control (C-F). In all charts,
 390 controls are shown in blue, HFHS in orange. *P<0.05; **P<0.01. The individual points that are plotted beyond the whiskers
 391 of the box-and-whiskers plots are extreme values larger than the 75th or smaller than the 25th percentile ± 1.5 -times inter-
 392 quartile range.

393

394 **3.5 Maternal HFHS diet reduces protein carbonylation but increases lipofuscin in the placenta at d16**

395 There was no significant increase in lipid peroxidation, a marker of oxidative damage at either gestational age (Figure 6A).
 396 In addition, protein carbonylation, also a marker of oxidative stress was significantly lower in the placenta of HFHS
 397 compared to control mice specifically at d16 (Figure 6A-B). The activity of the antioxidant GSH in the placenta was also
 398 similar between HFHS and control mice at both d16 and d19 (Figure 6C). However, lipofuscin formation, which is

399 associated with iron-dependent oxidative damage and ferroptosis [59], was increased in the placental labyrinth at both
 400 gestational stages by a maternal HFHS diet, with the effect statistically significant at d16 (Figure 6D-E).
 401

402
 403 **Figure 6: The effect of a HFHS diet on oxidative stress indicators and antioxidant capacity in the placenta at day 16**
 404 **and d19 of pregnancy.** Oxidative damage to lipids was measured by thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS)
 405 assay (A) and oxidative damage to proteins by 2,4-di-nitrophenyl-hydrazine (DNP)-mediated carbonyl quantification
 406 assays (B). The antioxidant potential was estimated by measuring the activity of total glutathione (GSH) (C). All assays
 407 were performed on placental tissue lysates from d16 and d19 (A-C; n=10-11/diet/age). Furthermore, lipofuscin an indicator
 408 of iron-dependent oxidative damage and ferroptosis was assessed by histologic detection and quantification of Sudan-
 409 Black-B (D-F; n=6-8/diet/age). A representative image of a HFHS placenta section at d16 is shown with the labyrinth
 410 depicted in blue and SBB-positive areas highlighted in yellow. Panel F demonstrates a high magnification (40x) close-up
 411 of the placental labyrinth, with yellow arrows pointing to SBB-positive lipofuscin. In all charts, controls are shown in blue,
 412 HFHS in orange. Statistical significance was determined using Mann-Whitney test, $\alpha=0.05$, *P < 0.05. The individual

413 points that are plotted beyond the whiskers of the box-and-whiskers plots are extreme values larger than the 75th percentile
414 plus 1.5-times inter-quartile range.

415 4 Discussion

416 The present study demonstrates that the maternal consumption of a HFHS diet during pregnancy alters placental iron
417 homeostasis in association with changes in fetal growth, independent of a change in maternal iron status. In particular, the
418 HFHS diet impacted placental iron transfer capacity, decreased placental iron content, and led to a dysregulation of genes
419 involved in ferroptosis, increased iron-dependent oxidative damage and stress kinase activation in the placenta. Changes
420 were dependant on gestational age and were related to reduced, and then subsequent enhanced fetal growth in this cohort
421 of HFHS diet-fed mice. Our results are largely in line with previous studies of the term, delivered human placenta from
422 women who developed GDM[44], as well as studies exposing trophoblast cell lines to hyperglycaemic conditions *in*
423 *vitro*[44]. Our findings, highlight the utility of this HFHS mouse model to study impacts of maternal metabolic disease
424 during pregnancy, as well as to inform on changes in placental iron handling with respect to fetal growth outcomes *in vivo*.

425

426 In the current study we found that fetal growth was reduced at d16, but then increased towards term (d19) in HFHS fed
427 mice. This is largely consistent with the altered pattern of fetal growth trajectory previously analysed in HFHS mouse
428 cohorts[45,46]. Moreover, like previous work using the HFHS mouse model, placental weight was reduced towards term.
429 The recovery and rapid elevation in growth of the fetus in late gestation despite a lighter placental weight in HFHS pregnant
430 mice is most likely a result of metabolic adaptation of the placenta through up-regulation of materno-fetal glucose, fatty
431 acid, and amino acid transport downstream of key signalling pathways, such as those involving insulin and the mechanistic
432 target of rapamycin (mTOR)[46,60–62]. Consistent with the relatively low content of iron in diets of industrialized
433 countries[2,5], our customized HFHS diet had a lower iron content than the control chow diet. Low dietary iron is associated
434 with changes in fetal and placental size in numerous species, including rodents and humans[63]. Although, the estimated
435 daily iron intake was around 5-times less in the HFHS group (chow control: 188mg/kg food iron content x 4.4g/day food
436 intake = 0.827mg/day iron intake per day; HFHS: 49mg/kg food iron content x 3.3 g/day food intake = 0.097mg/day iron
437 intake per day), our data demonstrated that maternal tissue iron levels (in liver and skeletal muscle) were maintained when
438 compared to the chow control group. This maintained maternal iron status was likely secondary to enhanced dietary iron
439 absorption, through the hepatic down-regulation of the master iron regulator hepcidin in the HFHS-fed dams[64]. Despite
440 this, we cannot fully exclude the possibility that differences in dietary iron availability contributed to the changes in
441 gestational outcomes seen in mice fed the HFHS diet.

442

443 The estimated placental capacity to uptake iron from the mother, as informed by the placental to maternal liver iron content
444 ratio and reduced placental TFR1 protein expression, was reduced at d16 in HFHS mice. Since the fetus depends on iron
445 for growth[63], the reduced placental iron uptake ability in HFHS fed mice likely contributed to the decrement in fetal
446 weight at d16. It may have also contributed to the diminished placental weight towards term in the HFHS mice reported
447 herein. At d19, placental TFR1 protein abundance was still reduced, but placental capacity to take up iron from the mother
448 was no longer decreased. Placental iron content and placental iron content relative to fetal weight were both reduced, but
449 fetal weight was enhanced in the HFHS group at d19. Previous work has reported that maternal consumption of this HFHS
450 diet led to morphological changes, including reduced fetal capillary volume and increased interhaemal membrane thickness
451 at d16 that were partially recovered by d19[46]. Whether morphological changes explain the altered placenta iron handling
452 and fetal growth trajectory in HFHS fed mice, however, will require further studies. Indeed, other work has suggested
453 relationships between materno-fetal substrate exchange, placental morphometric changes and fetal growth outcomes in
454 pregnancies associated with GDM[65], type-2 diabetes[66] and obesity[67]. In the present study, reduced placental iron
455 acquisition was related to decreased iron deposition in the decidua of the placenta in HFHS diet-fed mice at d16. These
456 data contrast previous findings where examination of gestational tissues from women with GDM revealed increased iron
457 storage within the chorion and decidua, namely in macrophages that showed an M2-like profile[68]. Thus, further work is
458 needed to assess the significance and cellular localisation of iron deposits in the placenta of the HFHS diet-fed mice.
459 Moreover, it needs to be elucidated whether iron accumulates in the decidua due to reduced transport across the placenta
460 *in vivo*[69], what could involve the low maternal hepcidin levels leading to higher release of cellular iron via FPN1[64].

461 However, it is important to note that iron transport across the placenta and regulation of fetal iron levels are complex
462 processes[14], so trying to identify precise changes and cause and effect relationships are likely to be challenging.

463

464 Altered placental iron handling was related to the disrupted expression of key iron homeostasis genes in the placenta of
465 mice fed the HFHS diet. In this context, increased placental expression of *Dmt1*, *Heph* and *Irf1* at d16 may reflect an
466 attempt to compensate for the impaired maternal iron uptake capacity of the placenta in HFHS mice at d16. For instance,
467 in response to low cellular iron levels, IRP1 binds to the 3'-iron responsive element (IRE) stem-loop structure within
468 untranslated regions of genes, that in turn, promotes the stabilization of mRNAs which increase iron uptake, namely *Tfr1*
469 for iron endocytosis and *Dmt1* for the transport of ferrous iron across the endosomal membrane into the cytosol[70].
470 Furthermore, HEPH is a multi-copper oxidase with ferroxidase activity that is crucial for cellular iron release by the iron
471 exporter FPN1[71], as *Fpn1* is targeted for degradation in the absence of ferroxidase activity[72]. In contrast to the up-
472 regulation of placental iron transfer genes at d16, there was a strong and harmonized down-regulation of the *Dmt1*, *Zip14*,
473 *Fpn1*, *Tfr1* and *Irf1* at d19 in HFHS diet-fed mice. The opposing regulation of iron handling genes at the two gestational
474 time points suggest a transition from increased to restricted materno-fetal iron transport between d16 and d19. However,
475 the down-regulation of TFR1 protein persisted in the placenta of HFHS mice, and was seen at both d16 and d19. According
476 to a recent gene cloning and ontology study, the TFR1 protein levels are predominately determined by the amount of *Tfr1*
477 mRNA available for translation[73]. However, other regulating factors, such as post-transcriptional regulation through the
478 interaction of IRPs as mentioned before is also possible[74]. In this case, the downregulation of *Irf1* and hence stabilization
479 of *Tfr1* mRNA at d19 could explain the reduced TFR1 protein levels. Previous *in vitro* studies trying to mimic
480 hyperglycaemic conditions of GDM in the human trophoblast cell line BeWo have shown an initial upregulation of *DMT1*
481 and Zrt- and Irt-like protein 8 (*ZIP8/SLC39A8*) after 3 days, followed by a stable downregulation of *DMT1*, *FPN1* and
482 *TFR1* mRNA after 20 days of continued hyperglycaemia exposure[44]. These results suggest that trophoblasts react upon
483 stimulation with diabetic-like conditions by an initial upregulation, followed by a reduction of placental iron transfer
484 mechanisms, that are consistent with our opposing observations between d16 and d19 in the placenta of HFHS mice in the
485 present study. We have previously shown that iron homeostasis genes are altered by GDM in the term human placenta
486 through an orchestrated downregulation of *DMT1* and *FPN1* mRNA, but also *ZIP8* and TFR1 protein[44]. Interestingly,
487 these changes were mostly reflected in murine placentas at term (d19) in response to the HFHS diet in the present study,
488 underlining a conserved impact of disturbed glucose handling on placental iron homeostasis.

489

490 The lower iron content of the HFHS compared to chow control diet may have also contributed to the changes in iron
491 homeostasis gene expression seen in the placenta. For instance, it has been previously shown that wildtype dams fed with
492 iron deficient diet exhibit increased placental *Tfr1*, *Dmt1* and *Fpn1* expression[69,75]. Although, obesity is associated with
493 higher hepcidin and therefore lower dietary iron absorption[19], maternal iron status as measured by liver and muscle iron
494 levels was not reduced in the HFHS diet-fed mice in the present study. Taken collectively, these findings indicate that the
495 reduced placental iron uptake and tissue content and deposition in the present study resulted from changes in placental iron
496 regulation, rather than from lower dietary iron levels or reduced iron absorption. As mentioned before, the reduced food
497 iron availability in the HFHS diet was tackled by downregulation of hepcidin and likely increased dietary iron absorption.
498 The observed alterations in placental iron handling genes may also reflect part of a protective mechanism that serves to
499 prevent oxidative damage in the fetus and placenta. Although lipid peroxidation in the placenta at d16 was not significantly
500 increased, and protein carbonyl formation was reduced at d16 in mice fed the HFHS diet, and lipofuscin accumulation
501 elevated in the placental labyrinth[59]. Lipofuscin is known to accumulate iron, which in turn, can generate oxidative stress
502 through the Fenton reaction and is associated with ferroptosis [59,76]. As we found lower placental iron yet decreased
503 protein carbonylation and increased lipofuscin, further work is required to understand the relationships between these
504 factors in the placenta in the context of maternal obesity. Recent work using CRISPR-based functional genomics has found
505 the lysosomal protein prosaposin (PSAP) is responsible for controlling survival during oxidative stress in neurons derived
506 from induced pluripotent stem cells[76]. Notably, this study demonstrated that knockdown of PSAP resulted in the
507 formation of lipofuscin, which traps iron, generates ROS and triggers ferroptosis[76]. Although PSAP was not measured
508 in the current study, collectively these data suggest a similar mechanism may be in operation and could explain the
509 disparities between iron mishandling and oxidative stress markers in the placentas from HFHS mice.

510

511 In general, oxidative damage occurs when ROS levels exceed antioxidant defences[3]. However, GSH as main
512 antioxidative opponent of ferroptosis was not significantly induced in dams fed the HFHS diet neither through upregulation
513 of *Gpx4* mRNA expression nor increased GSH activity. Interestingly, we found increased expression of the oxidative stress
514 and pro-ferroptotic gene *Nox2* alongside increased expression or abundance of the anti-oxidant catalase in the placenta of
515 HFHS dams. Our findings agree with others showing increased ROS levels and anti-oxidant imbalance in the placenta
516 involving increased catalase expression in various rodent models where type 1 and type 2 diabetes were induced via genetic,
517 surgical and pharmacological methods[77–79]. However, it is also likely that the present HFHS diet, which was just fed to
518 the mother during pregnancy, was not sufficiently severe to provoke an overall increase in lipid peroxidation or to exhaust
519 the antioxidative potential of the placenta. The present study demonstrates that maternal obesity seems to induce mild
520 oxidative damage in the placental labyrinth whilst simultaneously increases antioxidative potential via CAT up-regulation
521 in late gestation. These findings also highlight that the length of HFHS diet feeding, magnitude of diet-induced obesity
522 and/or hyperglycaemia exposure are important for determining placental oxidative responses.

523

524 Alongside with the detection of mild oxidative damage and an antioxidant imbalance in the placentas of HFHS diet-fed
525 pregnant mice, signalling pathways, namely the MAPK pathway can act as indicators of ferroptosis activation in the
526 placenta and trophoblast[14,80]. The p38 and JNK1 branches of the MAPK family are particularly suspected to mediate
527 ferroptosis downstream of lipid-related ROS[81], but this can be cell-specific[82,83]. In the current study, the increased
528 levels and/or activation of MAPK p38, JNK1 and ERK2 in the HFHS group may therefore indicate a degree of ferroptosis
529 in the placenta[58]. We also found upregulation of *Nox2* by the placenta in HFHS mice, and NOX2 is implicated in the
530 generation of ROS, is associated with ferroptosis[84] and is positively regulated by p38MAPK[85]. Prior work in a rat
531 model of metabolic disease (insulin resistance) has also reported changes in iron deposition, activated ERK/p38/JNK and
532 ferroptosis induction at the feto-maternal interface[86]. However, unlike that rat model of metabolic disease, which showed
533 significantly augmented oxidative stress[86], the mRNA expression of anti-ferroptosis genes, including *Gclc*, *Gss* and
534 *Gpx4*[87] and other pro-ferroptosis genes, such as *Acs14*[88], were not significantly altered in the placentas from HFHS
535 diet-fed mice at either gestational age. Therefore, it is possible that gestational changes in iron uptake by the placenta of
536 HFHS diet-fed mice prevented a complete oxidative derailment, and in turn, a significant induction of ferroptosis. It is also
537 important to note that in addition to their involvement in ferroptosis, MAPKs are involved in several other cellular
538 processes. ERK kinases are responsible for trophoblast growth and differentiation, p38-kinases serve as mediators of
539 oxidative stress pathways and apoptosis, and JNK, regulates apoptosis and immune cell responses[89]. Hence, further
540 mechanistic studies are needed to understand the significance of the genes and pathways affected in the placenta and how
541 these precisely relate to iron handling, ferroptosis and oxidative stress in the HFHS mice.

542

543 This integrative study of maternal and placental iron handling has key strengths that include examining changes at multiple
544 levels (genes, proteins, enzyme activity, histology) at two key different stages of gestational development in an established
545 diet-induced mouse model of metabolic disease during pregnancy. However, this study was limited by the lack of fetal
546 tissues other than placenta, such as fetal haematopoietic organs and fetal blood. Therefore, knowing if fetal iron supply and
547 status are affected in our model remains to be determined. Further work is also needed to causally test the association
548 between fetal growth deviations and placental iron mis-handling. According to the National Research Council, 35mg/kg
549 dietary iron is needed to meet the requirements of nonpregnant mice[90]. However, higher concentrations may be necessary
550 for pregnant animals, but also iron overload can be harmful[91]. Although the specific dietary iron requirement of pregnant
551 mice is unclear, the daily intake of dietary iron was ~0.83mg/day for the control chow group (188mg iron per kg chow
552 diet) and ~0.16mg/day for the HFHS-fed mice (49mg iron per kg HFHS diet), which could be considered iron-overload
553 and iron-deficiency[69], respectively. As measured, maternal liver and muscle iron levels did not differ with the gestational
554 diets. Future work is therefore required to fully understand the contribution of varied dietary iron intake and characterise
555 maternal iron status in our gestational HFHS mouse model. Further studies should also consider strategies to enhance the
556 maternal metabolic state, as well as the oxidative challenge of pregnancy, e.g., through additional glucose or iron to provoke
557 a more pronounced pathological condition and/or by introducing the HFHS diet prior to pregnancy. Alternatively, an
558 induced ferroptosis model may be employed to study consequences for pregnancy outcomes, such as involving an

559 engineered cyst(e)inase that causes systemic ferroptosis by degradation of both cystine and cysteine[92,93]. Since we were
560 not able to include groups in which different maternal parameters, such as maternal adiposity, hyperinsulinemia,
561 hyperglycaemia, and dietary iron deficiency were solely modified, we do not know which of these variables, in isolation
562 or in combination contribute to the outcomes we found in our HFHS mice. Therefore, much further work is required to
563 identify the specific mechanisms underlying the changes in placental and fetal growth phenotype in response to maternal
564 diet-induced obesity. Finally, fetal sex was not determined and therefore, the role of fetal sex in our outcome measures
565 could not be assessed. This will need to be addressed in future work, as fetal sex can influence the placental response to
566 environmental/gestational insults[94–99].

567

568 **4.1 Conclusions**

569 Collectively, our data show that gestational exposure to a HFHS diet alters placental iron homeostasis in association with
570 changes in genes and proteins implicated in iron handling, stress and ferroptosis signalling, as well as feto-placental growth.
571 These findings have implications given the increased intake of diets containing high amounts of fat and sugar in women at
572 reproductive age in Western and industrialised societies. They may also have relevance more broadly for understanding
573 possible consequences of the use, or lack, of iron supplementation in pregnant women. Most pertinently, these results are
574 highly relevant given that the rates of obesity and GDM are increasing in many parts of the world and are associated with
575 negative pregnancy outcomes and long-term effects on mother and child.

576 **Author contributions**

577 ANS-P, CA, JZ designed the study. ANS-P, ALF, BM undertook the mouse work. JZ and JL-T undertook the histological
578 and molecular work. JZ, ANS-P and CA wrote the paper, which was edited and approved by all co-authors.

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875 Statements and Declarations

876 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.